

1 **Cholinergic and nicotinamide signaling mobilization in mice with Wallerian degeneration mutation.**

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Harnessing regenerative responses in the central nervous system for spinal cord injury and paralysis is the holy grail of stem cell research. We conducted genome-wide expression screening for discovery of genes important for axonal regeneration and regeneration in the spinal cord using a mouse model of the Wallerian degeneration mutation and an amphibian (Salamander) model of spinal cord regeneration following axotomy. We report identification of genes functioning in nicotinamide metabolic pathways as well as those functioning in cholinergic signaling among those most differentially activated in *in vivo* models of regeneration in the CNS. *Nmnat1*, *Naprt* and *Nnmt* were among those most robustly induced at 2, 4 and 7 weeks post-injury in Wallerian degeneration mutant mice. In the cholinergic system, genes encoding receptors *Chrna4* and *Chrna6* were most significantly induced following axotomy in the Wallerian degeneration mutant mouse. A nicotinamide metabolic signaling pathway is active in regenerative responses in the CNS in mammals. An inflammatory response characterized by a complement cascade response and an axon guidance module containing *Slit2* and *Nrp1* were mechanistically associated with nicotinamide metabolic engagement following axotomy in Wallerian degeneration mutant mice *in vivo*.